

**PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF FACTORS SHAPING
DEMONSTRATIVE AND AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN
ADOLESCENTS****Yunusova Guzal Sultonovna**

Associate Professor of the Department of
Psychology, Fergana State University. Doctor
of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychological Sciences.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20353435>

ARTICLE INFOReceived: 18th May 2026Accepted: 20th May 2026Online: 22nd May 2026**KEYWORDS**

*aggression, demonstrativeness,
boys, girls, psychologists,
upbringing, adolescent*

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the factors that give rise to the demonstrative and aggressive behavioral characteristics observed in the personalities of boys and girls during adolescence. In addressing the topic, the theoretical views of psychologists who have conducted scientific research in this field have been studied and comparatively analyzed.

In the present era, the task of nurturing a well-rounded individual has become more pressing than ever, and the moral and ethical maturity, as well as the mental and physical vigor of the younger generation, takes on particular importance.

Under complex and turbulent modern conditions, parents, teachers, the public, and representatives of the mahalla are required to further strengthen their awareness and vigilance. We must not hand our children over to strangers but keep them within our own upbringing. To this end, it is necessary to speak more with young people, to listen to their hearts, to know their pain, and to provide practical assistance in solving their problems. In particular, serious attention must be paid to working with young people who are not engaged with any organization. In addressing these tasks, our national traditions formed over centuries and the rich heritage of our ancestors serve as our support. Every effort is being mobilized so that our children may master modern knowledge, professions, and foreign languages, become healthy and well-rounded individuals in every respect, and find a worthy place in life. Proceeding from these heartfelt thoughts of our country's leader, the study of the psychological state of young people — in particular, adolescents, who are the future of our homeland — and the reduction of the level of demonstrativeness and aggressiveness in their behavior renders this topic relevant.

The five important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in March 2019 serve precisely this purpose. These initiatives include the broad engagement of young people in the fields of culture, art, and sports, the formation of skills for the rational use of modern information technologies, the enhancement of reading culture, and the provision of employment for women. At the press conference, representatives of the relevant ministries and organizations responsible for the implementation of these initiatives — including the Youth Affairs Agency, the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Physical Culture and Sports, the Ministry for Development of Information Technologies and Communications, the Ministry of

Mahalla and Family Support, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the Information and Mass Communications Agency, the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment, and the Writers' Union — reviewed the work carried out and the tasks to be performed in the coming years.

The knowledge given to the younger generation is the firm foundation of our homeland's future. The more firmly this foundation is built, the more durable it will be, the more it will resist collapse in any situation, and the more it will astonish with its grandeur even as the years pass. The reforms being carried out today by our President, and the decrees and orders being adopted, are precisely actions aimed at strengthening this foundation. Only morally and physically well-rounded young people possessing an independent and resolute approach can give a worthy response to the threatening processes taking place on the global stage.

In shaping the personality of an adolescent, it is necessary to take into account his attitude toward the surrounding environment, toward social events, and toward people. Research conducted by psychologists shows that the majority of adolescents correctly understand such moral and ethical concepts as determination, modesty, pride, sincerity, and amiability. As a result of mastering the fundamentals of science in their life experience, stable convictional and scientific worldviews are formed, on the basis of which moral ideals begin to emerge.

As is known, during adolescence the "Self" of the personality is re-formed. The adolescent's attitude toward those around him, especially toward himself, his interests, and his system of values undergo sharp changes.

The psychologically most important trait of adolescence is the emergence of the sense of maturity, or of being an adult. This feeling finds expression in the social-moral sphere, in mental activity, in interests, in interpersonal relations, in the process of affection, and in the external forms of behavior. By studying the psychological characteristics peculiar to adolescence, one can understand the paths of the personality's formation, development, and maturation, as well as the direct influence of the biological and social factors that affect it. Sexual maturation acts as the principal biological agent influencing the adolescent's behavior at this age; however, this influence is indirect in character. The inability to get along that is observed in younger adolescents compared with older ones should be linked not with their sexual maturation but with the surrounding circumstances — the attitudes of parents and siblings within the family, and the influence of the mahalla, that is, of the social environment. By changing the psychological climate within these social conditions, it is possible to exert a direct influence on the adolescent's behavior and to prevent such negative traits as poor conduct, stubbornness, and unwillingness to acknowledge shortcomings. During this period, the adolescent finds himself in an intermediate state — he has bid farewell to a happy childhood but has not yet found his place in the life of adults. Without correctly assessing his abilities and strength, he attempts to solve complex life problems, but because his capacity for thought is superficial, he makes many mistakes in everyday life. Yet rather than admit his error, he prefers to argue with adults. He does not like those who criticize him; every criticism seems to him a sign of disrespect, a deliberate act. He strives to act independently and in his own way, and pays no heed to the advice of adults.

Demonstrativeness consists of purposeful, conscious acts aimed at making a certain impression on those around, at manifesting oneself in a distinctive way, at “playful” behaviors, and at overestimating oneself and emphasizing the “Self-image.”¹ Adolescence, as a transitional stage, is considered a complex, difficult, and critical period. Often it passes through hardship and gives rise to various deviations. In certain cases, the following are observed in the conduct of minors:

- consumption of alcoholic beverages and narcotic substances;
- theatricalized acts and acts of attempted suicide among adolescents;
- joining groups and subcultures united around various ideas.

Researchers unanimously conclude that demonstrativeness is one of the characteristic features of adolescent behavior. In A.E. Lichko’s view, the demonstrative reaction is “the most frequently encountered among the affective reactions in adolescent behavior.”

The desire to stand out from others manifests itself in several directions. Depending on the situation, the adolescent may switch from one style to another, or, if the result of the current style satisfies him, may keep it unchanged. The first style is to evoke respect, admiration, and sympathy toward one’s personality. This style yields good results in school and home settings. Here, the adolescent tries to stand out through his achievements in studies, in sports, or in some club activity. Often, the adolescent attributes his failures in studies to external factors. The second style consists of actions aimed at obtaining the pity and sympathy of those around him. Various means are chosen for this: from stories about his own misfortunes, to falling into hysteria, losing consciousness, and even becoming ill.

The third style is attracting the attention of those around in a negative manner. Here, such elements appear in the adolescent’s conduct as bravado, clowning, rudeness, deliberate breaches of discipline, going against the opinion of the majority, and other deviations in behavior. Demonstrative running away and demonstrative attempted suicide are also among these.

According to G.Parens, aggressiveness is a means of defending oneself and one’s rights. A.A.Rean and S.L.Solovyova also support this view. Aggression may give rise to the manifestation of unpleasant traits in a person’s character: in its fearless form, as hooliganism, and in its fearful form, as the inability to defend one’s rights. In addition, aggression alternates with other forms of delinquent and criminal behavior. The variability of the forms of manifestation of aggressiveness is characteristic of adolescents. L.M.Semenyuk (1996) investigated the various manifestations of aggressiveness at different stages of adolescence. According to her findings, in adolescents aged 10-11, physical aggression is predominantly observed. At this age, indirect aggression is encountered less frequently than other types of aggression. In adolescents aged 12-13, negativism is more prevalent, followed by forms of physical and verbal aggression. At the ages of 14-15, verbal aggressiveness comes to the fore; the forms of physical and indirect aggression, as well as the level of negativism, also rise markedly. There are also gender differences in the manifestation of aggressive reactions. In

¹Kravchenko A.S. Motivation of Demonstrative Behavior: abstract of dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Psychological Sciences. Moscow: M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, 2001. 102 p.

boys, the method of physical aggressiveness predominates. In girls, however, verbal aggression, indirect forms of aggressiveness, and the level of negativism increase.²

In the adolescent's mastery of the methods of expressing his own aggression, the relationships among brothers and sisters within the family serve as the principal foundation. This view found confirmation in Felson's study (Richardson D., Baron R., 1997). According to the results of the study, adolescents direct the greater part of physical and verbal aggression toward their sisters and brothers. It has also been established that the attitude of parents toward their child's aggressiveness has a significant impact on the relationship between the child and the parents. While parents try to eliminate the negative relations between children, they may, on the contrary, become the cause of the further expansion of these negative relations.³

This is clearly evident in the indirect form of aggressiveness and in negativism. The manifestation of aggressiveness in an adolescent and the form in which it emerges depend on the family environment in which he lives, on the company of peers, on the macro-environment (the educational institution), on the customs and traditions of society, and on the type of information flow reaching him. In this, the family plays the decisive role. This includes the relationship of husband and wife to each other, the mutual relationship between parents and child, the moral rules in the family, the worldview, and the plans and goals of the family.

References:

1. Decree No. PF-5847 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 8 October 2019 "On approval of the concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030."
2. Kravchenko A.S. Motivation of Demonstrative Behavior: abstract of dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Psychological Sciences. Moscow: M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, 2001. 102 p.
3. K.Yu. Gulyaeva, "Aggressiveness in Adolescence and Its Correction," UDC 159.96+159.94+316.6, 23.12.2006.
4. R. Baron, D. Richardson – Aggression. Saint Petersburg, 1997. 104 p.

²K.Yu. Gulyaeva, "Aggressiveness in Adolescence and Its Correction," UDC 159.96+159.94+316.6, 23.12.2006.

³R. Baron, D. Richardson – Aggression. Saint Petersburg, 1997. 104 p.